

STRAINLESS MONOCYCLIC RINGS. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF 2-METHYL-CYCLOHEXANESUCCINIC ACID AND THE SEPARATION OF ITS ISOMERS.

BY MUHAMMAD QUDRAT-I-KHUDA, AKBAR ALI MALLICK
(IN PART) and ASHUTOSH MUKHERJI.

2-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid, on being carefully separated, gives four isomeric modifications, melting respectively at 162°, 155°, 153° and 142°. The individuality of the acids has been proved by a study of the properties of their anilic acids, as well as the imides. Of the four acids, two are capable of undergoing change into the other two, through their anhydrides. The same phenomenon has also been observed in the case of the *m*-methylcyclohexane-succinic acids described in a previous communication. The work is now complete, leaves no doubt as to the validity of the hypothesis of release of strain in cyclohexane ring, under certain conditions.

In Parts I and II, it has been shown (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 6, 277; 1938, 16, 462) that by introducing substituents inside the cyclohexane ring it is possible to isolate isomeric compounds as required by the multipaner configurations of the methylcyclohexane ring. The present communication deals with the isolation of the different isomeric succinic acids (I) from *o*-methyl-cyclohexanone.

This acid has been prepared by the same general method, as adopted in the case of its *para*- and *meta*-methyl analogues. The separation of these acids, through their ammonium salts, has not been possible as in the previous cases, most of the acids undergoing conversion into a mixture of their imides in an attempt to convert them into the ammonium salts.

As the result of a series of very careful experiments it has been found that they could be separated satisfactorily with the help of solvents. A mixture of acids (I) was obtained by the hydrolysis of ethyl 1-methylcyclohexane-2-cyano-2-cyanoacetate (II), obtained by the addition of potassium cyanide to the unsaturated cyanoester (III).

The product of hydrolysis, on treatment with benzene, gave an acid (M), which when carefully crystallised melted at 162° . From the mother-liquor, two acids, one (P), m. p. 142° and the other (O), m. p. 153° , were obtained. All the three acids crystallised from ethyl acetate. When the acid (O) was converted into its anhydride, a liquid, b. p., $142^\circ/8$ mm. was obtained (the boiling point of the anhydride of P was $160-62^\circ/8$ mm.). But when the anhydride of (O) was decomposed by water, the only product was the acid (P), m. p. 142° . The same anhydride yielded an anilic acid identical with that of (P), m. p. 140° .

A very careful search was made for the fourth acid in the products of hydrolysis of ethyl 2-methylcyclohexane-1-cyano-1-cyanoacetate (II), but to no purpose. The inter-conversion of the two acids (P) and (O) opened up the question whether the acid (M) was also capable of undergoing change into another acid. The anhydride of the acid (M), b. p. $202^\circ/24$ mm., on hydrolysis gave an acid, m. p. 155° , and not 162° . That this lowering is not due to the presence of any impurity, has been proved. Neither does it appear to be identical with the acid (P), because there is a distinct lowering in its m. p. when mixed with this other acid.

A comparative study of the mixed m. p. of the different acids has been made and the results are given below in Table I, which shows definitely that all the four acids are actually different from one another.

TABLE I.

M. p. of acids.		Mixed m. p. of acids.	
M	162°	M & P	$148-49^\circ$
N	155°	M & N	$149-50^\circ$
O	153°	M & O	144°
P	142°	N & O	144°
		N & P	140°
		O & P	139°

Other derivatives of the acids, such as the anilic acids and the imides have also been made and purified very carefully for the determination of their individual melting points, as also their mixed melting points. The results are tabulated below in Tables II and III. These also suggest that the acids are distinctly separate entities. The m. p. of the acid (M) (162°), obtained from *o*-methylcyclohexanone, although very close to the melting point of the acid (C) from *m*-methylcyclohexanone, their difference has been demonstrated by the lowering of the m. p. to 147° . Similar difference is also shown by their derivatives.

TABLE II.

M. p. of the anilic acids of			Mixed m. p. of	
M	(W)	150°	W & X	143°
N	(X)	143°	W & Y	138°
O	(Y)	140°	W & Z	139°
P	(Z)	140°	W & Y	137°
			X & Z	135°
			Y & Z	139-140°

TABLE III.

M. p. of imides of			Mixed M. p. of	
M	R	107°	R & S	105°
N	S	110-111°	R & T	97-98°
O	T	98°	R & U	103-4°
P	U	105°	S & T	95-96°
			S & U	105-6°
			T & U	97-98°

Work on the intermolecular changes of the acids from 4-methylcyclohexanone is now in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 1-methylcyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate was prepared in the usual way but the yield of the product never exceeded 50% of the theory, after repeating the condensation several times with *o*-methylcyclohexanone and cyanoacetic ester, in presence of small amounts of piperidine. On redistillation, the unsaturated ester boiled at 165-67°/41 mm. and had d_4^{20} , 1.0248, n_D^{20} , 1.481736 whence $[R.]_D$ found, 57.54 and calculated, 56.36. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 7.99. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 69.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

The unsaturated cyano ester (100 g.) was condensed with potassium cyanide (60 g.) in the usual way, the yield of the acid being satisfactory, only when the condensation mixture was allowed to stand for at least 2 weeks. The hydrolysis of the dicyano ester also took a long time. Not less than 48-50 hours' heating on an wire-gauze would hydrolyse it fairly completely. From the above quantities the mixture of acids obtained amounted to 70 g. only. The acid was purified by dissolving it in a solution of sodium carbonate, from which on acidification the major quantities of the acids were precipitated out. The mother-liquor on evaporation to dryness on a water-bath, and extraction with ether yielded the acid (O).

Separation of the Acids.

The crude mixture of the acids was heated with benzene on a water-bath for 45 minutes with a reflux condenser each g. of the acid mixture requiring 5 c.c. of benzene. It was then filtered hot and the solid acid that remained was washed with cold benzene (about 100 c.c.). The residue consisted of the pure acid (M), m.p. 162° after crystallisation from ethyl acetate. [Found: C, 59.6; H, 7.8. M. W. (by titration), 202. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent. M.W., 200].

The *anhydride* of the acid (M) was obtained by heating the acid (10 g.) with acetic anhydride (25 c.c.) and acetyl chloride (2 c.c.) for 6 hours on a sand-bath. After the reaction was over, the fraction distilling at 202°/24 mm. was collected.

The *anilic acid*, obtained from the anhydride, crystallises from dilute alcohol, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 7.94. $C_{16}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 69.8; H, 7.6 per cent).

The *p-toluidinamic acid* was obtained from the anhydride and crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 179°. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 8.0. $C_{17}H_{23}O_3N$ requires C, 70.6; H, 7.9 per cent).

The *p-toluidinimide* was obtained from the corresponding toluidinamic acid on heating the latter in a sulphuric acid bath at 185-95° for 25 minutes. It crystallises from alcohol, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 75.63; H, 8.0. $C_{17}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 75.3; H, 7.8 per cent). *β-Naphthylamic acid*, obtained from the anhydride, crystallises from ethyl acetate, m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 73.6; H, 6.8. $C_{20}H_{23}O_3N$ requires, C, 73.8; H, 7.0 per cent).

The corresponding *β-naphthylimide* crystallises from alcohol, m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 78.6; H, 7.0. $C_{20}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 78.4; H, 6.8 per cent).

The *imide* of the acid (M) was obtained by heating the ammonium salt of the pure acid. When the decomposition was complete, the mass was washed with water and crystallised from dilute spirit. It was obtained as shining flakes, m.p. 107°. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.0. $C_{10}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 66.3; H, 8.3 per cent).

Pure anhydride of the acid (M) (1.2 g.) was heated with water on a water-bath for 8 hours. A solid acid (N) gradually separated out, which after being crystallised from water and then from ethyl acetate melted at 155°. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 7.9 per cent). It was converted into the *anhydride* when a liquid anhydride, b.p. 157°/12 mm., was obtained, which when decomposed with water gave the same acid, m.p. 155°. The anhydride yielded an *anilic acid* which crystallised from dilute spirit, m.p. 143°. (Found:

C, 69.9; H, 7.5 per cent). The anilic acid is apparently different from the anilic acid previously described and a mixed m. p. determination with equal portions of the two anilic acids showed a definite depression to 143° . The *imide* of the acid was prepared through the ammonium salt and crystallised from hot water, containing a small quantity of alcohol, m. p. $110-111^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

Acids (P) and (O).

From the benzene mother-liquor after the separation of the acid (M), the solvent was removed on a water-bath and the residual semi-solid mass allowed to stand over a week, when a small quantity of the solid separated out. It was then triturated with small amount of cold benzene and filtered. The acid was found to be the same acid, m. p. 162° . From the filtrate, the solvent was removed once again and the residue was esterified in the usual way. It was found, however, that heating the alcoholic mixture on a water-bath for 6 hours was necessary in order to effect a better separation. The product was isolated in the usual way, and it could be separated into two portions, one acidic and the other neutral. The neutral portion consisted mainly of an ester, b. p. $147-48^{\circ}/18$ mm; and gave $d_{4}^{26} 1.03164$, $n_{D}^{26} 1.45737$ whence $[R_{L}]_{D}$ found 67.63 ; calc., 67.90 : (Found: C, 65.4; H, 9.2. $C_{14}H_{24}O_{4}$ requires C, 65.6; H, 9.3 per cent).

The *ester* was next hydrolysed by means of 15% hydrochloric acid by heating for 18 hours on a sand-bath to an acid, m. p. 151° , which on being crystallised from ethyl acetate melted at 153° . This has been called acid (P). (Found: C, 59.8; H, 8.3 per cent).

The *anhydride* of the acid (P) boiled at $142^{\circ}/8$ mm. It gave an *anilic acid*, which crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 140° . (Found: C, 70.2; H, 7.6 per cent). The *anil* crystallised from very dilute alcohol, m. p. 105° . (Found: C, 74.7; H, 7.3 per cent). *p-Toluidinamic acid* separated in needles from alcohol, m. p. 187° . (Found: C, 70.6; H, 7.9 per cent). *p-Toluidinimide* crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 130° . (Found: C, 75.1; H, 7.5 per cent). The *imide* of the acid obtained from the ammonium salt of the pure acid crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 98° . (Found: C, 66.4; H, 8.4 per cent). The acid was regenerated from the *anhydride* when it melted at 141° and not at 153° which is the m. p. of the original acid.

The acidic portion of the product of esterification consisted of an acid ester. It was obtained as a thick viscid mass, but the silver salt was

obtained as a solid product. (Found: Ag 31.9. $C_{12}H_{19}O_4Ag$ requires Ag, 32.2 per cent). It was found, however, that if the esterification process was continued for more than 6 hours, some of the second acid was also converted into the neutral ester and the product of hydrolysis of the neutral ester then yielded a mixture of the two acids one melting at 153° and the other at 142° . When the acid ester previously obtained was hydrolysed with 15% hydrochloric acid by heating on the sand-bath for the same period as the neutral ester, on cooling, a mass of crystalline solid separated which when crystallised from ethyl acetate melted at 142° . This has been called acid (O). (Found: C, 59.8; H, 7.8 per cent). The *anhydride* of the acid, prepared as usual, boiled at $160-62^\circ/8$ mm. This, however, was found to give the same anilic acid, m.p. 140° and an anil, m. p. 105° , as the other acid (P). The *p-toiuidinamic acid* also melted at 187° , thus showing that the anhydride actually gives the same derivatives as the other anhydride. The regeneration of the acid from the anhydride gave the same acid, m. p. 142° .

The *imide* of the acid, prepared from the pure acid, was found to be a different one. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 105° . (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.4 per cent).

Grateful thanks of one of us (A. T. M.) are due to the Director of Public Instruction, Bengal, for the award of a research scholarship, which has enabled him to carry on this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received August 22, 1938,